

Nonlinear Power Measurement Algorithm of the Input Mix Components of the Noise Signal and Pulse Interference

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Abstract : A power measurement algorithm of the input mix components of the noise signal and pulse interference is considered. The algorithm efficiency analysis has been carried out for different interference to signal ratio. Algorithm performance features have been explored by numerical experiment results.

Keywords : noise signal, pulse interference, signal power, spectrum width, detection

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